

Quantum Spatial and Momentum Wavefunctions and Fourier Transforms

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In previous notes, we considered writing $P(x \text{ intersection } p)$, the probability of x intersection p as $W(x) \int \sin(px)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, \int its Fourier transform and $\sin(px)$ a term which models inherent zitterbewegung motion of quantum particle. It was argued that $W(x) \int \sin(px)$ described a kind of quasiparticle term with $W(x)$ describing interactions with other p momentum quasiparticles. Summing over p yields $W(x)W(x)$ which is the quantum mechanical density. In this note, we wish to consider a more generalized form of this quasiparticle, namely $G(x) \int \sin(px)$ where $G(x)$ and \int are no longer Fourier transforms of each other. We then consider finding the lowest possible energy such a system can have subject to the average energy at each point in space being equal to the total energy E . This yields multiple forms for $G(x)$, for example $G(x)=W(x)$ or $G(x) = W(x) + a$ (Function orthogonal to $W(x)$). We consider the case of the harmonic oscillator and try to show that $G(x)$ not equal to $W(x)$ actually has a higher entropy than $G(x)=W(x)$. The latter, however, matches experiment. Finally, we try to use the cycling resonance argument to show that there would be contradictions using $G(x)$ not equal to $W(x)$.

Energy Eigenvalue Equation

In (1), we considered that a quantum particle with inherent zitterbewegung modeled by $\sin(px)$ (backward and forward wave) can be placed in a potential $V(x)$ which will scatter it into many p states. It was assumed that the average kinetic energy plus $V(x)$ at each point x equaled E , the total energy:

$$\left[\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} \int \sin^2(px) \right] / \left[\sum_p \int \sin^2(px) \right] + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

with $\left[\sum_p \int \sin^2(px) \right]$ being a normalization constant called $W(x)$, the wavefunction. ((1)) can be rewritten as the time-independent Schrodinger equation with the Laplacian operator bringing in the factor p^2 in the kinetic energy. From this differential equation, one can show there are orthonormal eigenfunction solutions $B_i(x)$ with positive eigenvalues q_i . These functions $B_i(x)$ should form a complete set which can be used as a basis for expressing any other function.

Generalized Quasiparticle

In (3), it was argued that one could describe a particle scattered by $V(x)$ the potential as: $W(x) \int \sin(px)$ where $W(x)$ represents the interactions with other scattered states at point x , \int is the momentum weight of the particular p state and $\sin(px)$ represents the inherent zitterbewegung motion. It was assumed that $W(x)$ and \int were Fourier transforms of each other. Summing over p yields $W(x)W(x)$, quantum mechanical density.

In (2), it was argued that quantum mechanical spatial density could be obtained in the following manner:

$$P(p/x) = \int f(p) \sin(px) / W(x) = P(x \text{ intersection } p) / P(x)$$

$$P(x/p) = \int W(x) \sin(px) / f(p) = P(x \text{ intersection } p) / P(p) \text{ so}$$

$$P(x)/P(p) = \int W(x)W(x) / f(p)f(p)$$

From this it was argued that $P(x) = \int W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = \int f(p)f(p)$ with $W(x)$ and $f(p)$ being Fourier transforms of each other.

Here we wish to generalize the argument to describe a quasiparticle as $G(x)f(p) \sin(px)$ with $G(x)$ not being the Fourier transform of $f(p)$. In other words, $P(x/p) = \int G(x) \sin(px) / f(p)$ with $f(p)$ being the Fourier transform of $G(x)$. In such a case, the quantum mechanical density becomes $\int W(x)G(x)$.

It is argued that ((1)) still holds, as one is imposing the condition that average energy equal E at each point in space. In such a case, one uses $f(p)$ and $W(x)$ as these describe $P(p/x)$ which is needed to obtain the kinetic energy at x . Already, $W(x)$ and $G(x)$ are not being treated on the same footing, and this perhaps suggests that there are problems with this generalized $G(x)$.

Consider ((1)) and multiply by $W(x)G(x)$. Then one obtains:

$$\sum_p G(x) p^2 / 2m \int f(p) \sin(px) + V(x)G(x)W(x) = E \int G(x)W(x)$$

Integrating over x yields $\sum_p p^2 / 2m \int f(p) + \int dx V G W = E \int G W$.

Minimization of Energy to find the Ground State

Consider now finding the lowest energy, i.e. the ground state. From ((1)) we know that there are a series of orthonormal eigenfunctions $B_i(x)$ with positive eigenvalues q_i with q_0 being the lowest. Thus, one may start with $W(x) = B_0(x)$ to obtain a lowest energy. The question then becomes: What is $G(x)$? It should be written as

$$G(x) = \sum_j a_j B_j(x) \quad ((2))$$

as the $B_j(x)$ functions are complete. Given that the integral of density $\int G(x)W(x)$ must be one and that the $B_j(x)$ are orthonormal, $a_0 = 1$. Thus, $G(x)$ is still undetermined and so is the quantum mechanical density. A further condition is that $G(x)W(x) > 0$ for each x , where $W(x) = B_0(x)$. The physical density needs to be positive everywhere. This, it seems, can cause some problems for ((2)) if one uses all $B_j(x)$ values, but it may be possible to include some B_j 's. The issue is that $\int B_0(x)G(x)$ must be positive. Assume for the case of argument that $B_0(x)$ is positive everywhere,

then $G(x) - B_0(x)$ must be positive in some places and negative in others, such that these positive and negative values, multiplied by $B_0(x)$ cancel. (B_0 is orthonormal to $G(x) - B_0(x)$.) The density is:

$$B_0(x)B_0(x) + B_0(x) \sum_j a_j B_j(x) \quad ((3))$$

If $B_0(x)$ is very small in some places, say δ , then $B_0(x)B_0(x)$ is $\delta \cdot \delta$. The $\sum_j a_j B_j(x)$, however, might be negative in such a place forcing one to make the a_j very small (less than δ) to ensure that the overall density stays positive. " a_j ", however, is a constant, so if it is tiny in one place, it is tiny everywhere meaning one is not really including $B_j(x)$ terms in $G(x)$. Consider also the case of $B_0(x)$ having zero values. Near such values $B_0(x)$ will be very small meaning that $\sum_j a_j B_j(x)$ must be very small if it is negative at such a point. This again leads to tiny a_j values.

It is, however, possible to consider a case where one can have a $G(x)$ which includes $B_j(x)$ values. Consider the case of the harmonic oscillator. The ground state is a Gaussian peaked at $x=0$. $B_2(x)$ is a function with a negative hump at $x=0$, so one include it in the description of $G(x)$ without making the coefficient arbitrarily small. Thus, it seems that one can have a $G(x)$ not equal to $B_0(x) = W(x)$.

Maximum Entropy Considerations

Given that one can have a $G(x)$ that is not $W(x)$, this means that different functional forms of $G(x)$ still give a density which is everywhere positive, integrates to 1 and represents the same ground state energy. How does one choose among these? Let us consider using entropy arguments, with entropy given by $-k \sum P_n \ln(P_n)$ where P_n are probabilities. For the case here, we use density as a probability, thus $S = -k \int W(x)G(x) \ln[W(x)G(x)]$. The question becomes, what is the change in S if one changes $G(x)$?

$$\text{Change in entropy } S = -k \int \delta[G(x)] W(x) \ln[W(x)G(x)] - k \int W(x) \delta G(x) \quad ((4))$$

Where $\delta G(x)$ means the change in the functional form of $G(x)$.

Consider integrating over x . Then the term $-k \int W(x) \delta G(x)$ vanishes because it equals $\sum_j [\Delta a_j] \int B_j(x)$ and $W(x) = B_0(x)$ is orthogonal to these. Thus, only the first term in ((4)) is important. Now $W(x)G(x)$ is a density so it is positive, but less than one in value.

One can consider a specific example, namely $B_0(x) = \exp(-x^2/2)$, the ground state of an oscillator and $\delta G(x) = a(2x^2 - 1)\exp(-x^2/2)$ where $a > 0$ and the function is $B_2(x)$ for an oscillator (4). Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Change in entropy} &= - \int dx \ln(B_0 B_0) B_0 \delta G(x) \\ &= \int dx (x^2/2) \exp(-x^2) a (2x^2 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

This integral can be performed by multiplying by integral $dy \exp(-y^2)$ and converting to polar co-ordinates $r dr d\theta$. The r integrals can then be converted using $x^2 = z$ which leads to integrals with $\exp(-z)$ which can be solved using integration by parts. The overall result seems to be that the change in entropy going from $G(x) = B_0(x)$ to $G(x) = B_0(x) + a B_2(x)$ is positive, i.e. there is more entropy. Experimentally, however, the density is $W(x)W(x)$ which means that one must choose $G(x) = W(x) = B_0(x)$.

Cycling and Contradiction of Having $G(x)$ not equal to $W(x)$

In the cycling approach (3), it was suggested that in the Schrodinger equation the term $V(x)W(x)$ from ((1)) (obtained by multiplying by $W(x)$) represented "waves" in the potential $V(x)$ interacting with waves in $W(x)$. To see this, $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ were both written as Fourier series and then the various $\exp(ikx)$ from $V(x)$ combined with the $\exp(ipx)$ from $W(x)$. Grouping terms by overall $\exp(iqx)$ one can see that cycling occurs with a frequency of E . Thus, if there were a $G(x)$ and a $W(x)$ one could consider two different cycling schemes $V(x)W(x)$ and $V(x)G(x)$, but there is only one occurring in the system. The energy equation ((1)) is written in terms of $W(x)$ and it seems that this is all that is needed. Thus, there seems to be no reason to try to generalize density to $G(x)W(x)$ as $W(x)W(x)$ is self-consistent and the generalization would lead to some contradictions in a cycling picture.

Conclusion

In conclusion, one can try to postulate a more general form for quantum density, namely $W(x)G(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction and $G(x)$ describes interactions with the potential $V(x)$ at each point x . This would be in keeping with a quasiparticle picture of motion, namely $G(x) \propto \sin(px)$ instead of $W(x) \propto \sin(px)$. If one uses conservation of energy at each point x with $W(x)$ being used in such an equation, one can show that by finding the lowest energy state, multiple functions of $G(x)$ would be allowed. This leads to the problem of choosing which one applies. One could have $G(x) = W(x)$ or $G(x) = W(x) +$ a linear combination of weighted orthogonal functions such that $G(x)W(x) > 0$ at each x and is normalized. We consider a case where such a density actually has a higher entropy, while still yielding the same average energy. Experimentally, however, it is $G(x) = W(x)$ which is the solution. We revisit cycling arguments and suggest that it would be a contradiction to have $G(x)$ not equal to $W(x)$. It is already strange that one has $G(x)$ and $W(x)$ and yet writes an energy equation for only $W(x)$.

References

- 1, Ruggieri, Francesco R. Logarithm of Wavefunction as Partition Function (preprint, zenodo, 2018)
- 2, Ruggieri, Francesco R. Spatial Motion in Quantum Mechanics and Wavefunction Squared as Density (preprint, zenodo, 2019)

3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. 2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2018)

4. Harmonic Oscillator Wavefunciton

<http://hyperphysics.phy-astr.gsu.edu/hbase/quantum/hosc5.html>